

The Carpentries

*Growing Inclusive, Computational
Communities and Leaders*

2019

A message from our Executive Director

What an incredible year 2019 has been! My favorite moments include onboarding Regional Coordinators in New Zealand, Southern Africa, and the Nordic Countries, releasing the first iteration of our Curriculum Development Handbook, our June lesson release (36 lessons were published!), the excitement we received from the community about our Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility Roadmap, CarpentryConnect Manchester, and of course, the release of our vision statement, nine core values, and strategic plan. This year we also bid farewell to The Carpentries first Executive Director, Dr. Tracy Teal. We are extremely excited about all that the organisation accomplished under her leadership, and as your Executive Director I cannot tell you how proud I am of the work our Core Team and community is undertaking during this transition.

Of the many challenges and opportunities (“choppportunities”) we prepared for in 2020, one could not have expected to face a global pandemic. We must now adjust the ways we work together and prioritise our work as COVID-19 continues to impact us in unprecedented ways. We understand the impact this crisis has on our community as the world shifts to virtual instruction. The importance of digital skills is undeniable; educators and organisations are rallying together to support effective instructional strategies.

The Carpentries supports 1,700+ highly skilled instructors and an established digital skills curricula. We have experience training educators. We are uniquely positioned to support the shift in the nature of education around the world. With \$2.65 million in funding from the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation and Chan Zuckerberg Initiative for scaling our instructor training and curriculum development programs, we are ready to respond to this challenge. Now more than ever we need you to champion our mission. Let’s rise to the occasion - together.

Onward.

Kari L. Jordan

Kari L. Jordan, PhD
Executive Director

A message from our Executive Council

In 2018, Data Carpentry, Library Carpentry, and Software Carpentry came together as a single organisation, dedicated to building a stronger community for teaching the computational skills we believe are key to research in many different fields. In 2019, members of each of these Lesson Programs contributed to our community-wide efforts to express our joint Mission, Vision, and Values that will provide guideposts and touchpoints for the broader organisation as we reach out to more people in more places and in more languages.

This second year of being The Carpentries has transformed our community from a loose conglomeration of individuals into a unified organism working in support of a defined set of community values. We are proud of our substantial growth of community members and increases in global participation and are excited that our new members are beginning their experiences under this unified Carpentries identity. We may be working across heterogeneous domains, audiences, and experience levels, but our shared mission and vision bind us together. The Executive Council's goals for 2020 are to move forward priorities identified on the strategic plan developed by the 2019 Executive Council, and to continue to grow strategically while developing innovative methods of sustainability and scaling across the globe.

Amy Hodge
Chair, 2019

Elizabeth Wickes
Chair, 2020

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Pictured left to right, bottom - Amy Hodge, Karen Cranston, Joslynn Lee, top - Tracy Teal, Kate Hertweck, Lex Nederbragt, Raniere Silva, Juan Steyn, on screen - Elizabeth Wickes, not pictured - Mesfin Diro Chaka.

Our Values

act openly, empower one another, value all contributions, always learning, inclusive of all, people first, access for all, community collaboration, strength through diversity

Grow with us.

Our Mission

The Carpentries builds global capacity in essential data and computational skills for conducting efficient, open, and reproducible research. We train and foster an active, inclusive, diverse community of learners and instructors that promotes and models the importance of software and data in research. We collaboratively develop openly-available lessons and deliver these lessons using evidence-based teaching practices. We focus on people conducting and supporting research.

2019 Highlights

In partnership with our community, we articulated our **vision statement** - to be the leading inclusive community teaching data and coding skills - along with the **core values** that define our community ethos. We established a **strategic plan** to guide our work in line with these values over the next three to five years and we joined with our community to express **gratitude** for one another in our varied roles.

The theme of our inaugural global conference in 2018 was “Building Locally, Connecting Globally.”

Our community has since held four **regional conferences** on as many continents to continue strengthening their local communities. Our team of **volunteer Regional Coordinators** supports the work and culture of The Carpentries in their geographical areas, ensuring communities can **thrive locally**.

We **received funding** from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, California Digital Library, and Mozilla Open Source Support Program. Combined, this funding supports scaling of our instructor training, curriculum development, and community development programs, as well as our equity, inclusion, and accessibility efforts.

We **strengthened our infrastructure** to better support our growing community, making it easier for community members to schedule virtual meetings, reporting learner feedback in a format more useful for workshop instructors, and streamlining processes so our core team can support **more workshops more efficiently**.

Moving forward

In the first half of 2020, we are focusing on hiring and onboarding **new Core Team members** to support our curriculum development, community development, and instructor training programs. This includes working with our fiscal sponsor Community Initiatives to develop a **sustainable and scalable approach to international contracting** - enabling our Core Team to become more representative of our global community. We are also bringing onboard our **new Executive Director**, who will lead our Executive Team in guiding the strategic direction of The Carpentries.

To help our community meet the challenge of COVID-19, we are establishing processes for **delivering our workshops online**, while maintaining our high quality of instruction, real-time feedback, and one-on-one support for learners.

In the remainder of the year, we will be developing **continuing education offerings** for instructors, improving **accessibility** of our website and lesson template, refining our **communications strategy**, and **updating our membership model** to fit organisations at different stages in their development as a self-sufficient Carpentries community. It's going to be quite a year!

Since 2012, we have run **2,300** workshops in **61** countries and trained **2,400** volunteer instructors to deliver our **33** collaboratively developed, open lessons to **56,900** novice learners at our **85** member sites and beyond.

In 2019, we trained 684 instructors an increase of 29% from 2018.

We ran 554 workshops. An increase of 16% over the previous year.

83% of learners surveyed would recommend Carpentries workshops to a friend or colleague.

Our Financials

Fiscal year January 2019 to December 2019

Q1 Finances	USD	Q2 Finances	USD	Q3 Finances	USD	Q4 Finances	USD
Income	\$281,935	Income	\$420,656	Income	\$337,595	Income	\$1,633,539
Expenses	\$319,394	Expenses	\$362,116	Expenses	\$350,922	Expenses	\$498,874
Net Income	(\$37,459)	Net Income	\$58,540	Net Income	(\$13,327)	Net Income	\$1,134,664
Cash Available	\$99,148	Cash Available	\$157,689	Cash Available	\$144,362	Cash Available	\$1,279,027

Our Financials

Fiscal year January 2019 to December 2019

Income by Category	USD	Percent
Grants & Sponsorships	\$1,556,927	57.98
Memberships	\$877,828	32.69
Instructor Training	\$131,246	4.89
Workshops	\$113,015	4.21
Donations	\$6,386	0.24
Total	\$2,685,402	100.00

Expenses by Program	USD	Percent
Administration	\$496,460	32.42
Community Engagement	\$213,385	13.93
Membership	\$174,312	11.38
Fundraising	\$169,627	11.08
Workshop Administration	\$153,195	10.00
Curriculum Development	\$129,490	8.46
Instructor Training	\$112,030	7.32
Communications	\$82,808	5.41
Total	\$1,531,306	100.00

Expenses by Category	USD	Percent
Personnel	\$1,022,515	66.77
Fiscal Sponsorship	\$279,187	18.23
Professional Fees	\$131,317	8.58
Meetings & Travel	\$55,248	3.61
Software & Subscriptions Services	\$28,725	1.88
Supplies, Utilities & Space	\$13,052	0.85
Marketing & Communications	\$1,261	0.08
Total	\$1,531,306	100.00

Thank you and congratulations to The Carpentries community
for all the impactful and inspiring ways that you contribute!

Carpentries Core Team Members
CarpentryCon Task Force Members
Champions
Community Initiatives Staff
Code of Conduct Committee Members
Curriculum Advisory Committee Members
Executive Council Members
Helpers
Hosts
Independent Contractors
Instructor Development Committee Members
Instructors
Instructor Trainers
Learners
Library Carpentry Advisory Group
Lesson Infrastructure Committee
Lesson Maintainers
Member Organisations
Regional Coordinators

Further Together!

<https://carpentries.org>

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